

LCA and TEA

Ammonia Cracking and Renewable Hydrogen: Environmental Insights from RED III and LCA Methodologies

ABSTRACT

The info-packs present an environmental assessment of the proton ceramic electrochemical reactor (PCER) with Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) and Renewable Energy Directive III (RED III) methodologies, within the EU Horizon project SINGLE. Short descriptions of LCA and RED III methodologies and key differences are presented together with the results of the environmental assessment, with focus on the carbon footprint. The assessment includes only the operation phase of the PCER and excludes the emissions from ammonia production. The carbon footprint is higher when using the LCA methodology due to the wider scope of the system. Under the assumed conditions, the carbon footprint of the use of the PCER is below the RED III threshold for renewable hydrogen.

Key points

- LCA methodology provides a more complete environmental assessment than RED III methodology.
- Under the assumed conditions, the use of the PCER places ammonia cracking below the RED III carbon footprint threshold for renewable hydrogen, allowing for up to 2,910 kg CO₂ eq. emissions in the upstream part of the value chain.

Introduction

The ambitious *EU Green Deal* aims to import 10 million tons of renewable hydrogen. Given the challenges associated with long-distance hydrogen transport, particularly the need for high pressures for gaseous and low temperatures for liquid hydrogen, ammonia offers a promising alternative. Hydrogen can be converted to ammonia for easier storage and transportation, then converted back to hydrogen at the point of use through ammonia cracking. The production and cracking of ammonia are energy-intensive processes. The transportation and storage energy intensity depend on the type of transport and storage, and the potential conditioning needed. The *SINGLE* project focuses on ammonia cracking technology with a PCER that integrates ammonia dehydrogenation reaction, hydrogen separation, heat management, and compression in a *SINGLE* stage.

While the entire ammonia and hydrogen value chains will be assessed from an environmental perspective, the primary focus is on the PCER. Since the EU defined its own methodology (RED III) for determining if hydrogen is renewable or not, this calculation is also included and compared to the standard LCA analysis. The first goal of the study is to assess the PCER operational phase with LCA. Secondly, the same PCER system will be assessed using the RED III methodology to determine the carbon footprint of ammonia and estimate the potential gap to the threshold value required for compliance with renewable hydrogen criteria. Finally, the results from both methodologies will be compared to highlight key differences.

Methodology

The LCA methodology is a method standardized by the ISO standards ISO 14040 and ISO 14044 for assessing the environmental impacts in the life cycle phases of products or processes. The LCA methodology is scientifically recognized as a suitable methodology for assessing environmental impacts. The scope of the LCA methodology typically extends from cradle to grave but can be narrowed while still complying with ISO standards, provided the scope is clearly and transparently documented. In addition, the system boundaries and assumptions are arbitrary and must be stated transparently. The LCA methodology includes/offers several Life Cycle Impact Assessment (LCIA) methods, each defining a distinct set of environmental impact indicators.

The EU RED III is an important legislative framework to advance the European Union's renewable energy targets as part of the *European Green Deal* and the *Fit for 55* package. Within RED III directive a methodology for renewable hydrogen is specified and it targets only one environmental indicator – carbon footprint. The methodology introduces a "simplified" lifecycle analysis of the hydrogen value chain. The analysis scope shall include the emissions related to energy use in the production process, conditioning, and transportation of renewable fuels of non-biological origin (RFNBOs), including the emissions occurring at the end of customer's use of hydrogen.

For hydrogen, the threshold is 28,2 g CO₂ eq./MJ H₂ or 3,384 kg CO₂ eq./kg H₂.

The most important simplifications compared to the standardised LCA methodology are:

- The upstream emissions for energy refer only to the supply of fuels (i.e. extraction, refining and transport).
- Emissions associated with the production of machinery and equipment are excluded from the assessment.
- The use of renewable energy sources is considered emission-free.

For example, the emission factor for Spanish electricity grid mix is 0,195 kg CO₂ eq. for RED III methodology and 0,237 kg CO₂ eq. for LCA methodology, due to these simplifications.

More detailed comparison of LCA and RED III methodologies is presented in SINGLE's workshop highlights¹.

SINGLE case

Here, the results of the operational phase of the PCER are presented using both the LCA and RED III methodologies, with a focus on carbon footprint. Only the core technology is assessed, excluding the balance of plant. The impacts of ammonia production and transportation to the site are not included in this study. Spain is selected as the location of the PCER operation site. It is assumed that 70% of the electricity is supplied by an on-site PV solar plant, while the remaining portion is sourced from the electricity grid. Total electricity consumption is 7,06 kWh/kg H₂². The LCA calculation was performed with the Sphera database and the Environmental Footprint 3.1 LCIA method was used for environmental assessment.

Results

The results indicate a higher carbon footprint when using the LCA methodology, primarily due to its broader system boundary. LCA calculation includes SINGLE unit production, PV electricity, electricity from grid mix, and water production, while RED III includes only emissions from electricity from grid mix. Electricity from grid mix is the main hotspot in the LCA study. PV electricity contributes 16% to the total carbon footprint and SINGLE unit production contributes 10%. The impact of the water production is negligible (<0,2%). The results for 1 kg of hydrogen production are presented in the figure below.

With the use of PCER under assumed conditions, 2,910 CO₂ eq. of carbon footprint can still be emitted upstream of the PCER for ammonia production and transportation.

Conclusions

LCA methodology is a holistic methodology for the assessment of environmental impacts widely used in the scientific community. RED III is a legislative framework which, together with some other documents, defines the threshold for hydrogen, and other RFNBOs, to be considered as renewable hydrogen.

The LCA is applicable to any product or process and assesses from “cradle to grave”, while RED III is only applicable for RFNBOs and is limited to “well to wheel” assessment. The LCA also includes variety of environmental indicators, while RED III evaluates only the carbon footprint.

Due to the enlarged scope of the LCA analysis, the carbon footprint is higher if calculated with the LCA methodology compared to the RED III. The GHG emissions from SINGLE unit production, PV electricity, and water production are not accounted for under the RED III methodology, but they contribute to the overall impact in the LCA assessment. The main hotspot in LCA analysis is electricity from the Spanish grid, which contributes 73% of the entire carbon footprint. The study indicates that only 14% of the RED III carbon footprint threshold for renewable hydrogen is emitted in the cracking process, meaning that up to 2,910 kg CO₂ eq. can be emitted upstream of the PCER site (ammonia production and transportation).

1 J. Gramc, D. Hojkar, A. Lotrič, and M. Mori, “Workshop SINGLE project highlights: Application of the LCA and RED III methodology to assess GHG emissions in the SINGLE ammonia value chain,” 2025.

2 D. Clark et al., “Single-step hydrogen production from NH₃, CH₄, and biogas in stacked proton ceramic reactors,” *Science* (1979), vol. 376, no. 6591, pp. 390–393, 2022, doi: 10.1126/science.abj3951.

Authors

Jure Gramc, *Researcher at UL*
jure.gramc@fs.uni-lj.si

Andrej Lotrič, *Post-doctoral researcher at UL*
Andrej.lotric@fs.uni-lj.si

Domen Hojkar, *Researcher at UL*
domen.hojkar@fs.uni-lj.si

Mitja Mori, *Associate professor at UL*
mitja.mori@fs.uni-lj.si